

Extractive Method of Separation of Lead(II) as Ethyl Xanthate from a Number of Ions in Solutions of Binary Mixtures

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Like zinc¹ and cadmium^{2,3} lead forms ethyl xanthate complex (1 : 2) which is completely extractable in chloroform and carbon tetrachloride. Its solitary extraction behaviour has been reported earlier³. The present communication reports an extractive method of quantitative separation of Pb^{II} from a number of ions as its ethyl xanthate in CCl₄, re-extraction (stripping) with suitable reagent and titration complexometrically (EDTA, hexamine, xylenolorange).

The effects of various cations and anions on a single

extraction of lead as ethyl xanthate under the conditions of general procedure³, viz. pH 5.5–6 (CH₃COOH/CH₃COOK), 2 drops of pyridine, equal volumes of extractant and aqueous solution, shaking for 2 min (~ 2 strokes/sec) have examined. The results are shown in Table 1. The distribution constant value of lead ($K_d = \text{concentration of Pb as ethyl xanthate in CCl}_4 / \text{concentration of Pb}^{II} \text{ in aqueous solution}$) at pH of the general procedure and at room temperature (~25°) has been determined through estimation of lead by atomic

TABLE I – EFFECT OF VARIOUS IONS ON LEAD EXTRACTION AS FOUND BY STRIPPING WITH NITRIC ACID (0.5N) AND EDTA TITRATION

Lead-xanthate system, Pb (2 mg), pH before extraction 5.5–6.0 (HAc/KAc)

Foreign ion mg	pH after extraction	Apparent extraction*	Foreign ion mg	pH after extraction	Apparent extraction*
Tl ⁺ (7.2) ^a	–	+ve	UO ₂ ²⁺ (5.0)	6.0	+ve
Zn ²⁺ (2.0)	6.0	+ve	VO ₃ ⁻ (5.0)	6.0	> 98
Cd ²⁺ (1.3)	6.0	+ve	H ₂ EDTA ²⁻ (5.0)	–	–ve
Cu ²⁺ (1.0)	6.0	–ve	H ₂ PO ₄ (5.0)	–	–ve
As ³⁺ (5.0)	–	+ve	Tartrate of		
Sb ³⁺ (5.0)	–	–ve	Na ⁺ , K ⁺ (25.0)	6.3	> 98
Bi ³⁺ (5.0)	6.0	+ve	HF ₂ ⁻ (5.0)	–	–ve
Hg ²⁺ (5.0)	6.0	+ve	CrO ₄ ²⁻ (5.0)	6.0	–ve
Fe ³⁺ (0.045)	6.0	+ve	S ₂ O ₃ ²⁻ (24.0)	6.5	–ve
Sn ²⁺ (5.0)	5.5	–ve	Oxalate (25.0)	6.2	> 98
Ni ²⁺ (2.0)	6.0	+ve	Citrate (25.0)	8.5	> 98
Co ²⁺ (2.0)	6.0	–ve	I ⁻ (25.0)	8.0	> 98
Cr ³⁺ (25.0)	5.5	> 98	SO ₄ ²⁻ (25.0)	7.5	> 98
Mn ²⁺ (25.0)	7.5	> 98	SCN ⁻ (25.0) ^a	6.0	> 98
			S ²⁻ (1.0) ^a	–	–ve

*+ve = positive interference, –ve = negative interference.

^aPb²⁺ taken 4.0 mg.

TABLE 2 – QUANTITATIVE SEPARATION OF LEAD FROM INTERFERING IONS IN BINARY MIXTURES

Quantities in mixtures (mg ratio) separated	Procedure
Pb ²⁺ : Zn ²⁺ (2 : 22)	The mixture is adjusted to pH ~ 6 (HAc/KAc). Reagent* and extractant are added successively and shaken (~ 200 strokes). Both are extracted. Zn ²⁺ is first stripped with NH ₄ OH/NH ₄ Cl buffer (pH ~ 10), then Pb ²⁺ is stripped with 0.5 N HNO ₃ . or The mixture is adjusted to pH 8–9 (NH ₄ OH/NH ₄ Cl buffer). The reagent* and the extractant are added successively, shaken (~ 200 strokes). Pb ²⁺ is extracted but Zn ²⁺ is retained in the organic phase. Pb ²⁺ is stripped with 0.5 N HNO ₃ .
Pb ²⁺ : Cd ²⁺ (17 : 1), (0.5 : 26)	Mentioned in the method of separation of cadmium from binary mixtures ² .
Pb ²⁺ : Hg ²⁺ (HNO ₃ or HCl) ^a (2 : 25)	The method applied in Cd ²⁺ /Hg ²⁺ separation ² is applicable. Only the stripping is performed twice. Pb ²⁺ is stripped. Hg ²⁺ is retained in the organic phase.
Pb ²⁺ : Bi ³⁺ (5 N HNO ₃) ^a (2 : 25)	The acidity of the mixture is reduced (NH ₄ OH) and adjusted to pH ~ 2. 5–6 ml of 2% reagent* solution and the extractant are successively added and shaken. Both are extracted. Pb ²⁺ is stripped by two stripping operations. Bi ³⁺ is retained in the organic phase.
Pb ²⁺ : As ³⁺ (2 : 25)	The pH of the mixture is adjusted to 5–6 (HAc/KAc). Successively the reagent* and the extractant are added and shaken. Both are extracted. Pb ²⁺ is stripped by two stripping operations with the same strippant. As ³⁺ is retained in the organic phase.
Pb ²⁺ : Sb ³⁺ (1 N HCl) (2 : 62)	The method applied in the Cd ²⁺ /Sb ³⁺ separation ² is applicable except the stripping solution in the present instance is 1N HNO ₃ , and 0.57% of the total Sb ³⁺ is co-stripped in the first operation.
Pb ²⁺ : Sn ²⁺ (1 N HCl) (2 : 10)	Applying the method of Cd ²⁺ /Sn ²⁺ separation ² but using the stripping agent 0.5 N HNO ₃ , 95% of the total Pb ²⁺ can be stripped. In case of Pb ²⁺ /Sn ²⁺ = 2 : 25, addition of a large quantity of KNO ₃ (to resist emulsion formation) and consecutive two extraction and stripping operations separate 90% of total Pb ²⁺ .
Pb ²⁺ : Fe ³⁺ ^a (6 : 0.5)	The pH of the mixture is adjusted to ~ 6 (HAc/KAc). Successively the reagent* and the extractant are added and shaken. Both are extracted. Pb ²⁺ is stripped by two stripping operations. Fe ³⁺ is retained in the organic phase.
Pb ²⁺ : Co ²⁺ ^b (2 : 10)	The pH of the mixture is adjusted to ~ 6 (HAc/KAc). Citrate is added to avoid scum formation. Successively, the reagent* and the extractant are added and shaken. Both are extracted. Pb ²⁺ is quantitatively stripped, but more than one extraction and stripping operations are necessary.
Pb ²⁺ : Cu ²⁺ ^a (2 : 10), (10 : 1)	The pH of the mixture is adjusted to 4–6 (HAc/KAc). The reagent* and the extractant are successively added and shaken. Both are extracted. Through two or more consecutive extraction and stripping operations Pb ²⁺ is quantitatively stripped. Cu ²⁺ is retained in the organic phase.
Pb ²⁺ : Ni ²⁺ ^c (2 : 11)	The pH is adjusted to ~ 7.5 (NH ₄ OH/NH ₄ Ac). The reagent* and the extractant are successively added and shaken. Both are extracted. Pb ²⁺ is stripped. Some Ni ²⁺ is co-stripped. The co-stripped Ni ²⁺ is separated from the stripping following the method adopted in the Cd ²⁺ /Ni ²⁺ separation ² .

Pb ²⁺ : UO ₂ ²⁺ (2 : 25)	The pH is adjusted to ~8 (glycine-NaCl/NaOH). The reagent* and the extractant are added successively and shaken. Both are extracted. Pb ²⁺ is stripped. U(VI) is retained in the organic phase.
Pb ²⁺ : Tl ⁺ ^d (4 : 41)	For complete separation of Pb from Tl the method of using the acid form of the reagent (XnH) in CCl ₄ as extractant ³ is adopted. The mixture is adjusted to ~ 0.3 N with HNO ₃ , extracted twice with CCl ₄ containing XnH ([Xn] ≈ 0.3 mM or 3.63 mg ml ⁻¹), first with a volume equal to that of the aqueous solution and then with a half of the volume of the same (~200 strokes each time). The organic phase after separation is washed twice with equal volume of ~ 0.025 N KOH solution. After every washing the KOH phase is further washed with a small quantity (~ 5 ml) of CCl ₄ and the latter is mixed with the original organic phase. The combined organic phase contains only lead and it is stripped with 0.2 N HNO ₃ . At least two stripping operations are necessary.
Pb ²⁺ : H ₂ EDTA ²⁻ ^e (2 : 25)	After adjustment of pH to ~ 6 (HAc/KAc) the reagent*, Al ₂ (SO ₄) ₃ solution and the extractant are successively added and shaken. Only Pb ²⁺ is extracted; it is stripped. H ₂ EDTA ²⁻ is retained in the aqueous phase.
Pb ²⁺ : CrO ₄ ²⁻ (2 : 25)	The pH is adjusted to 7.3 (NH ₄ OH/NH ₄ Ac). The reagent* and the extractant are added and shaken. Only Pb ²⁺ is extracted; it is stripped. Cr(VI) is retained in the aqueous phase.
Pb ²⁺ : S ₂ O ₃ ²⁻ (2 : 25)	The same procedure, as in the Pb ²⁺ /CrO ₄ ²⁻ system is applicable.
Pb ²⁺ : HF ₂ ⁻ (2 : 25)	The pH is adjusted to ~ 8 (glycine-NaCl/NaOH), the reagent* and the extractant are added and shaken. HF ₂ ⁻ is retained in the aqueous phase. Only Pb ²⁺ is extracted; it is stripped.
Pb ²⁺ : H ₂ PO ₄ ⁻ (2 : 25)	The same procedure as in the Pb ²⁺ /HF ₂ ⁻ system, is applicable.
Pb ²⁺ : S ²⁻ (Na ₂ S) ^f (4 : 1)	A mixture (1 ml Pb ²⁺ (4 mg) and 0.2 ml S ²⁻ (1 mg)) is adjusted to a pH 5-6 (HAc/KAc; 5 ml) and 5 ml of HgCl ₂ solution (2.3 mg Hg ²⁺ /ml), 3 ml of K-xanthate solution (3%) are added to it. A total volume of ~ 15 ml is adjusted with necessary volume of water, and shaken with ~15ml of CCl ₄ containing 2 drops of pyridine (~100 strokes). The phases are separated. The aqueous phase is washed with a further 5 ml of CCl ₄ . Both Pb ²⁺ and Hg ²⁺ go into the organic phase. Only lead is quantitatively collected from the organic extract by re-extracting it twice with equal volume of 0.5 N HNO ₃ .
	or
	To the mixture (1 + 0.2) ml, 2 drops of NaOH (0.1 N) and requisite volume of water are added to adjust to a volume of ~10 ml. Then extracted with XnH-CCl ₄ solution ³ , ([Xn] ≈ 2.52 mg/ml), first with 10 ml and then with 5 ml and finally with only CCl ₄ (5 ml). The organic extract is then stripped twice with HNO ₃ (~ 2 N).

*In the descriptions in Table 2 unless otherwise mentioned, the 'reagent' is the aqueous solution (4-5 ml) of 1% potassium ethyl xanthate, the 'extractant' is CCl₄ with 2-4 drops of pyridine. The immiscible phases are of equal volume (~ 20 ml), the stripping solution is HNO₃ (~ 0.5 N), the shaking rate is 2 strokes per second.

^a Addition of a few drops more pyridine helps to achieve both the aqueous and the organic phases clear for the binary mixtures with Cu^{II}, Hg^{II}, Bi^{III}, Fe^{III}. In these mixtures for high lead content, more than one extraction operation and several stripping operations using 0.5 N or stronger nitric acid may be necessary.

^b In a mixture containing 2 mg Pb²⁺ but increasing quantity of Co²⁺ needs more and more citrate; corresponding to 2, 3, 5 and 10 mg Co, the quantities of citrate used are 0.0, 3.5, 5 and 25 mg respectively.

^c 6% Ni²⁺ is co-stripped. This Ni²⁺ is removed from the stripping in the similar way as was adopted in the Cd²⁺/Ni²⁺ mixture; through chloroform extraction of Ni-DMG complex. 5-6 drops of 1% DMG are required.

^d Application of the general procedure mentioned in the text, or much higher concentration of Xn⁻ in the XnH-CCl₄ method used in this system, have been found to produce a brownish white scum at the interface. The scum formation in the present method has been avoided by using [Xn⁻] ≈ 0.03 mM/ml. Irrespective of the methods, the organic phase has been found to take a light brown tinge which can be removed by shaking it with a very dilute KOH solution (~ 0.025). The KOH washing does not affect the Pb²⁺ concentration in the organic phase. The end-point of the EDTA titration (xylenol orange) is not perfectly yellow; it has slight reddish tinge.

^e The conditional stability constant logK_{M'X'} of Pb-EDTA and Al-EDTA complexes at pH ~ 6.3 are respectively 11.9 and 9.9, but Pb²⁺ forms extractable xanthate at this pH whereas Al³⁺ does not form any xanthate.

^f Application of the general procedure can not extract more than 10% of the Pb²⁺ in the presence of S²⁻ in aqueous solution. Addition of S²⁻ after xanthate (a transposed order of addition) in the aqueous solution containing Pb²⁺ at pH 6 (HAc/KAc) does not extract (CCl₄) more than 25%. Pb(Xn)₂ is extractable in CCl₄ but not PbS. This suggests that PbS is more stable than Pb(Xn)₂. Again, addition of xanthate to mixture (Pb²⁺ and S²⁻) containing HgCl₂, at the same pH, extract both Pb²⁺ and Hg²⁺ as xanthate in CCl₄. This is possible due to the fact that (i) HgS is not extractable but Hg(Xn)₂ is, (ii) in water HgS is more stable than PbS (solubility products at 25° are 3 × 10⁻⁵³ and 1 × 10⁻²⁹ respectively), (iii) in water, perhaps, Hg(Xn)₂ is more stable than HgS, and (iv) in CCl₄ Hg(Xn)₂ is more stable than Pb(Xn)₂ (~3 N HNO₃ can not strip Hg²⁺ from a solution of Hg(Xn)₂ in CCl₄ (unpublished result). The course of reactions may be as

Application of a solution of XnH in CCl₄ as a complexant cum extractant has been found earlier to be more effective than addition of Xn⁻ to the aqueous mixture and then extraction with CCl₄.

absorption spectrophotometric method, and found to be 167. It is seen that Ti⁺, Zn²⁺, Cd²⁺, Cu²⁺, Hg²⁺, Sn²⁺, Ni²⁺, Co²⁺, UO₂²⁺, As³⁺, Sb³⁺, Bi³⁺, Fe³⁺, H₂PO₄⁻, HF₂⁻, CrO₄²⁻, S₂O₃²⁻, S²⁻, H₂EDTA²⁻ interfere.

Depending upon the nature of interference, the simple extractive method of quantitative separation of Pb^{II} (> 98%) from the above interfering ions are concisely described in Table 2. Whether a single extraction step can be adopted for a wide range of concentration ratios has also been tested, and illustrated with binary mixtures of Pb²⁺ with Hg²⁺, Bi³⁺, Fe³⁺ and Cu²⁺.

This quick extractive method of quantitative separation together with easy and accurate titrimetric estimation of lead may be used in routine analysis in binary mixtures with other ions in practical technological laboratories.

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